

Received: 03 March 2026 | Accepted: 29 May 2026 | Published: 15 June 2026

Open Access | RESEARCH REPORT

Exploratory longitudinal study of serum adipokines and lipid profile in breast cancer patients receiving adjuvant chemotherapy

Nikolaos Dogkas^{1,2,*} ,
George Albert Karikas² ¹Biochemistry Laboratory, General Anticancer Hospital of Piraeus METAXA, Piraeus, Greece²Department of Biomedical Sciences, School of Health and Care Sciences, University of West Attica, Athens, Greece

*Corresponding author: Nikolaos Dogkas, Biochemistry Laboratory, METAXA Anticancer Hospital, Piraeus, Greece; Tel.: +30 6936266962; email: ndogkas@uniwa.gr

ABSTRACT

Background: Adipose tissue is an active endocrine organ responsible for the production of adipokines. **Aim:** This study aimed to investigate whether serum levels of four adipokines (leptin, adiponectin, resistin, visfatin) and lipid parameters (cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol) are affected by adjuvant chemotherapy. **Methodology:** Twenty-five Greek patients who had been operated and received adjuvant chemotherapy with a good response were included. Blood samples were collected at three distinct time points during treatment, in order to measure the above parameters. **Results:** Cholesterol, LDL and HDL levels did not show statistically significant differences at the three time points. In contrast, triglycerides were statistically significant higher ($p=0.0030$) at the final time point. Serum leptin and resistin levels prior to treatment were significantly higher ($p<0.0001$) than those observed during mid- and end-treatment. Comparison between the mid- and end- treatment time points showed a statistically significant difference ($p<0.0001$), with higher levels observed at the mid-treatment time point. Serum adiponectin levels yielded a significant difference (lower value) between the baseline and the end time points ($p<0.0001$), as well as across the other time points. Visfatin levels were significantly higher at the baseline of the treatment compared to both mid- and end-treatment levels (both $p<0.0001$). **Conclusion:** Increased levels of adiponectin, together with decreased values of the other three adipokines, are consistent with the results from previous studies, suggesting their potential use as auxiliary parameters. Regarding lipids, only levels of triglycerides provide relevant information. However, due to the absence of a control group and the small sample size ($n=25$), these findings should be interpreted as exploratory and hypothesis-generating rather than confirmatory.

KEYWORDS

breast cancer, adipokines, lipids, adjuvant chemotherapy, longitudinal study

How to cite this article: Dogkas N., Trapali M., Fountzoula C., Karikas G. A., Karkalousos P.: Exploratory longitudinal study of serum adipokines and lipid profile in breast cancer patients receiving adjuvant chemotherapy. *Rev. Clin. Pharmacol. Pharmacokinet.* 40: 15-25 (2026).
DOI: [10.61873/rcpp.40.e190445](https://doi.org/10.61873/rcpp.40.e190445)

Copyright: © 2026 by the authors.
Licensee PHARMAKON-Press, Athens, Greece.

This is an open access article published under the terms and conditions of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC BY 4.0) license.

Publisher note: PHARMAKON-Press stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

1. INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, breast cancer (BC) is the most commonly diagnosed malignancy and the main cause of cancer-related death in women. High invasiveness, frequent recurrences, metastatic ability to brain and lungs, contribute to its severity [1]. Adipose tissue plays a key role as an energy storage depot and functions as an endocrine organ to produce various bioactive substances [2]. Epidemiological and etiological data have shown that conditions of abnormal distribution of adipose tissue, such as obesity, are an important risk factor and a negative prognostic factor for this malignancy [3].

Lipids are described as natural compounds, soluble in polar solvents and insoluble in water. They include small biomolecules with remarkable variation in structure [4]. It is well established that the composition and permeability of the cell membrane may be altered due to changes in lipid metabolism. This fact may be crucial for the development and progression of many diseases, including cancer. Concerning cancer, lipids may affect tumor growth and development. Proliferation is a significant feature of cancer cells, which requires a constant supply of lipids for the biosynthesis of their membranes and the modification of their proteins. Furthermore, non-renewing cells require significant amounts of lipids to support cell signaling and resist apoptosis. Lipoproteins transport both endogenously and exogenously derived lipids to the tissues, playing a fundamental role in the progression of cancer via the delivery of lipids to malignant cells and tumors [5-6].

The most important plasma/serum lipids from a clinical point of view are total cholesterol (TC) and triglycerides (TG) [7]. Cholesterol, despite its role as a major component of cell membranes, serves as a precursor for steroid hormones, vitamin D, oxysterols and bile acids. Cholesterol is required for neuronal signaling molecules to function. On the other hand, triglycerides represent the main energy source in the body. The hydrophobic nature of these biomolecules requires the presence of lipoproteins (complex lipid aggregates and proteins) which transport lipids between tissues.

Adipocytes are the primary cell population of adipose tissue, which is a type of connective tissue because its extracellular matrix is composed of proteins [8]. Especially in breast where there is a large concentration of adipose tissue, mature adipocytes and mammary epithelial cells are separated, under normal conditions, by a basement membrane that limits the interaction between them. However, during tumor

development, epithelial cancer cells penetrate the basement membrane and interact with adipocytes which then contribute to tumor progression. The extremely complex interaction between cancer-associated adipocytes (CAA) and cancer cells (breast cancer cells or BC) is not fully understood; however, it is known that CAAs communicate with BC cells through adipokines [9]. Dysregulation of adipose tissue function, as observed in obesity, has been associated with the development of several diseases, including cancer. It is estimated that obesity contribute to approximately 20% of cancers [10].

The most important secretory products of adipose tissue are "lipokines" or "lipocytokines". These molecules are protein hormones that are synthesized and secreted by adipocytes or by cells that are included in or filter the adipose tissue [11]. These include classic adipokines such as resistin, visfatin, leptin, and adiponectin; newer molecules such as apelin, nesfatin, and vaspin; as well as cytokines (e.g., TNF α , IL-6), chemokines (e.g., MCP-1), proteins of the alternative complement pathway (e.g., adipsin), enzymes (e.g., P450 aromatase), and other bioactive products such as angiotensinogen [12].

Leptin is a hormone with M.W equal to 16 kD. Adipose tissue is the main site of its secretion, which is proportional to tissue's mass. Serves as a message of satiety and energy adequacy, inhibiting appetite [13]. Leptin's receptor, a single transmembrane protein, expressed in most tissues, is responsible for hormone's action. Intracellular signaling pathways such as JAK/STAT3, MAPK, PI3K/Akt, ERK1/2, AMPK and IRS, are induced by this receptor [13-14].

Mechanisms of oncogenesis including (cell proliferation, invasion, angiogenesis and inflammation) are associated with the upregulation of specific gene transcription, activated by JAK2/STAT3 pathway [15]. Moreover, anti-apoptotic proteins, inflammation markers (TNF- α , IL-6), factors of angiogenesis (Vascular Endothelium Growth Factor) and the HIF-1 α , are over-expressed [16-17]. Cell division is promoted through activation of *c-fos* gene response elements following ERK phosphorylation. Subsequently, JAK2 activation, PI3K and Akt are phosphorylated, leading at glucose utilization, cell growth, cell proliferation and apoptosis [18]. Leptin has also been associated with breast cancer (BC) depending on the menopausal status. Respectively, there is a positive and negative correlation in post-menopausal and pre-menopausal women [19-20].

Adiponectin, a 244 amino acid monomer adipokine (also known as AdipoQ or Acrp30), with M.W equal approximately to 26 kDa, is the most

abundant peptide hormone, which secretion comes from white adipocytes and belongs to the family C1q/TNF proteins [21]. Its levels show an inverse correlation with the mass of adipose tissue and appear to have a protective effect against the appearance of various obesity-related disorders, such as metabolic syndrome, cardiovascular diseases and several malignancies [21].

Several receptors have been identified as binding sites for adiponectin: AdipoR1 (mainly expressed in skeletal muscles and endothelial cells), AdipoR2 (mainly hepatic expression), and T-cadherin [22-23]. Adiponectin receptors are widely expressed in different tissues, including cancer cells [15].

Adiponectin inhibits cell-proliferation, migration and is responsible for pro-apoptotic actions [24]. There is evidence that low serum levels of the hormone is an independent risk factor for breast cancer (BC) regardless of age, lymph nodes metastases, hormone receptor and menopause status [25]. Moreover, invasiveness may be determined by adiponectin's levels [26].

Resistin is another adipocytokine of 12.5 kDa. Mononuclear inflammatory and adipose cells, are responsible for its secretion [27]. TLR4 binds resistin and as a result the PI3K, p38 MAPK, and NF- κ B pathways, are activated. NF- κ B protein mediates and several inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1, etc.) and adhesion molecules, are produced. Adipocytes that penetrate adipose tissue, mostly express resistin. Thus, its serum levels are more likely to be associated with inflammation [28], supporting its role as adipokines potentially involved in cancer development. Resistin also acts as a link between obesity and increased inflammation, contributing to inflammation-associated tumor growth [29].

Visfatin, a 52-kDa protein is the product of the *NAMPT* gene. It is an enzyme, adipocytokine, and growth factor [29-30]. Visfatin exists in two forms, the Intracellular-iNampt and extracellular-eNampt. iNampt plays a role in NAD (electron carrier) biosynthesis, which is essential for cellular metabolism. On the other hand, eNampt is excreted by a variety of tissues such as adipose by cell lysis [30]. Diabetes, obesity, aging, atherosclerosis, cardiac hypertrophy, and autoimmune diseases, are associated with eNampt [31].

In oncogenesis, eNampt displays pro-inflammatory, proliferative, anti-apoptotic, and pro-angiogenic effects [32] by inducing inflammation through the activation of NF- κ B and promoting proliferation through the upregulation of Notch-1, cyclin D1, cyclin dependent kinase 2, MAPKs, ERK-1/2, and p38 signaling pathways [33-34]. Moreover, eNampt may act as an endocrine mediator in

some cancers and may contribute through its immunosuppressive properties to the characteristic immune-evasive properties of malignancies [35].

The aim of this clinical laboratory study was to evaluate adipokines (leptin, adiponectin, resistin, visfatin) and lipids (cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol) in BC patients who received adjuvant therapy (5-fluorouracil (5-FU), cyclophosphamide, doxorubicin, paclitaxel) at three predefined time points: baseline, mid-treatment, and end of treatment.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Study setting

The study was conducted at the Laboratory Chemistry, Biochemistry, Cosmetology of the Department of Biomedical Sciences of School of Health and Care Sciences of the University of West Attica, Athens, Greece from March 2021 to January 2024.

2.2. Participants

Twenty-five Greek patients were recruited for this study. The cases consisted of women with incident, pathologically confirmed breast cancer (BC), under age 64 (range 45–64 years), who had undergone surgery and received adjuvant chemotherapy. The participants had never been diagnosed with any other type of cancer. Moreover, they did not experience any infections during the study period and showed no significant change in body mass index (BMI) (change rate <5%). With regard to their dietary habits, the majority reported consuming breakfast, three main meals accompanied by a daily snack, and multiple servings of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains; with respect to meat intake, they exhibited a preference for fish and poultry, while red meat was consumed infrequently.

2.3. Sample collection

A total of 75 blood samples were collected (25 at each time point). Blood collection was performed under similar conditions early in the morning, after 8 h of fasting. Peripheral blood samples were centrifuged at 3,500 rpm for 10 min in the laboratory. Serum was separated and stored at -20°C , in aliquots of 500 μL , until analysis. This storage temperature ensures the stability of specimens containing a broad range of labile analytes, including adipocytokines and lipids.

2.4. Laboratory measurements

2.4.1. Adipokines determination

The serum concentrations of leptin, adiponectin, resistin and visfatin were measured using sandwich enzyme immunoassay ELISA RUO kits (Bertin Bioreagent Company for leptin and adiponectin, Origene for resistin and AssayGenie for visfatin). The leptin kit had a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.2 ng/mL, the adiponectin kit had an LOD of 0.47 ng/mL, the resistin kit had an LOD of 4 pg/mL, and the visfatin kit had an LOD of 0.188 ng/mL.

2.4.2. Lipids determination

We carried out photometric measurements of serum levels of cholesterol, triglycerides, and HDL-cholesterol using Beckman Coulter's automated analyzer AU5800, while LDL-cholesterol was estimated using the Friedewald equation: $LDL = Total\ cholesterol - HDL\ cholesterol - TG/5$.

2.5. Statistical analysis

The comparison of mean values at the three time

points of the treatment was carried out using one-way repeated-measures ANOVA. This method assumes approximate normality of the dependent variables and sphericity of repeated measurements, and accounts for the fact that the same patients were measured at all time points. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

2.6. Ethical approval

The study protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the General Anticancer Hospital of Piraeus "METAXA" (reference number 12367/27-01-2021) and the Ethical Committee of the University of West Attica (reference number 11914/17-02-2021). The principles of the Declaration of Helsinki were followed throughout the study involving human subjects. All patients were provided with an informed consent form containing information about the study, and their willingness to participate was confirmed by signature.

3. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the results for each lipokine at the three measurement time points during treatment, while Table 2 presents the significance levels (p -values) of comparisons between the mean values.

Table 1. Serum levels (mean \pm standard deviation) of the four adipokines at T1 (baseline), T2 (mid-treatment), and T3 (end of treatment).

	Time points of adjuvant therapy		
	T1 (baseline)	T2 (mid-treatment)	T3 (end of treatment)
Leptin (ng/mL)	36.68 \pm 15.76	26.19 \pm 11.84	19.49 \pm 8.80
Adiponectin (ng/mL)	27.27 \pm 19.34	34.74 \pm 22.58	43.47 \pm 25.45
Resistin (pg/mL)	18.53 \pm 6.94	10.96 \pm 5.18	8.64 \pm 5.35
Visfatin (ng/mL)	15.18 \pm 5.91	9.71 \pm 4.55	7.84 \pm 4.69

Table 2. P -values for comparisons of mean serum levels of the four adipokines at T1 (baseline), T2 (mid-treatment), and T3 (end of treatment).

Comparison	Comparisons between time points of adjuvant therapy		
	T1 vs T2	T1 vs T3	T2 vs T3
Leptin (ng/mL)	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Adiponectin (ng/mL)	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Resistin (pg/mL)	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Visfatin (ng/mL)	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001

The distributions of the four variables were approximately normally distributed. For the comparison of the three time points of the treatment, one-way repeated-measures ANOVA and post hoc Bonferroni's multiple-comparison tests performed.

A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Regarding leptin, serum levels at the beginning of treatment (36.68 \pm 15.76) were significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) than those during treatment

(26.19 ± 11.84) and at the end of treatment (19.49 ± 8.80). A significant difference was also observed between mid- and end-treatment levels ($p < 0.0001$), with higher values at mid-treatment. A decrease in values was observed across the three time points. However, due to interindividual variability, values may have been lower or higher than the mean. In this comparison, the results were statistically significant.

Serum adiponectin levels at baseline (27.27 ± 19.34) were significantly lower ($p < 0.0001$) than those at the end of treatment (43.47 ± 25.45). A statistically significant difference was also found between baseline and mid-treatment levels (34.74

± 22.58), as well as between mid- and end-of-treatment levels ($p < 0.0001$).

Regarding resistin, serum levels were found to be significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) before treatment than those in the middle of treatment, as well as those at the end of treatment. A comparison between the mid- and end-treatment time points showed significantly higher levels at mid-treatment compared to the end ($p < 0.0001$).

Serum visfatin levels at the baseline were significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) than those at mid-treatment and at the end of treatment. A similar result was also observed between the mid- and end-of-treatment time points.

Figure 1. Diagrams depicting the levels of four lipokines at three stages of adjuvant treatment: T1 (baseline), T2 (mid-treatment), and T3 (end of treatment).

Table 3 shows the results for each lipid at the three measurement time points during treatment, while

Table 4 presents the significance levels (p -values) for comparisons of the mean values.

Table 3. Serum levels (mean \pm standard deviation) of the four lipids at T1 (baseline), T2 (mid-treatment), and T3 (end of treatment).

	Time points of adjuvant therapy		
	T1 (baseline)	T2 (mid-treatment)	T3 (end of treatment)
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	184.10 \pm 33.77	185.30 \pm 28.03	185.80 \pm 25.66
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	118.70 \pm 30.61	123.20 \pm 29.72	126.50 \pm 28.13
LDL (mg/dL)	106.00 \pm 33.90	105.90 \pm 28.31	107.20 \pm 25.28
HDL (mg/dL)	54.24 \pm 7.43	54.64 \pm 6.90	53.24 \pm 6.48

Table 4. *P*-values for comparisons of mean serum levels of the four study lipids at T1 (baseline), T2 (mid-treatment), and T3 (end of treatment).

Lipids	Comparisons between time points of adjuvant therapy		
	T1 vs T2	T1 vs T3	T2 vs T3
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	>0.9999	>0.9999	>0.9999
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	0.080	0.432	0.0030
LDL (mg/dL)	>0.9999	>0.9999	>0.9999
HDL (mg/dL)	>0.9999	0.701	0.741

From the above data, no statistically significant differences were observed in the mean serum levels of cholesterol, LDL, and HDL across the three

time points. In contrast, for triglycerides, a statistically significant difference was observed only between mid-treatment and end-of-treatment levels ($p=0.0030$).

Figure 2. Diagrams depicting the levels of four lipids at three stages of adjuvant treatment: T1 (baseline), T2 (mid-treatment), and T3 (end of treatment).

4. DISCUSSION

Adipose tissue is a complex and metabolically active endocrine organ. Adipocytes, as well as the non-adipocyte fraction of adipose tissue, synthesize and secrete several hormones, such as leptin, visfatin, resistin and adiponectin, collectively referred to as adipocytokines.

Briefly, leptin serves as a primary regulator of adipose reserves and exerts multiple oncogenic effects, including the induction of cellular proliferation, promotion of angiogenesis, and inhibition of apoptosis [36]. In contrast, the roles of visfatin and resistin in carcinogenesis remain less elucidated. Preliminary research suggests that visfatin may contribute to the etiopathogenesis of breast cancer (BC) by accelerating cell cycle progression and upregulating genes essential for angiogenesis and metastatic potential [37]. Resistin, synthesized by adipocytes and predominantly by infiltrating monocytes, is primarily associated with inflammatory pathways. Although its definitive role in malignancy remains unclear, emerging evidence suggests a potential involvement in carcinogenic processes. Conversely, adiponectin has demonstrated potent antiproliferative properties across diverse breast cancer (BC) cell lines [38], supporting its characterization as a putative anticarcinogenic factor.

Our study indicated that baseline serum concentrations of leptin and resistin were significantly elevated relative to those recorded at mid- and post-treatment intervals. Longitudinal analysis revealed a further significant decline between the mid- and end-treatment time points, with the former maintaining higher values. Conversely, serum adiponectin levels were significantly lower at baseline compared to the study's conclusion, with distinct variances observed across all measured intervals. Finally, visfatin levels demonstrated a significant reduction from baseline to both mid- and end-treatment phases.

Elevated serum leptin concentrations have been implicated in the pathogenesis of breast cancer (BC) among both pre- and postmenopausal populations [39], as well as in hereditary predispositions [40]. Conversely, adiponectin is recognized for its tumor-suppressive properties, mediated through the inhibition of the Wnt and Akt signaling pathways [41]. Furthermore, postmenopausal breast cancer patients exhibit significantly higher serum resistin levels [42-45], suggesting a possible prognostic role for resistin. This association has also been observed in premenopausal cohorts [44], thereby aligning the present findings with established literature. Regarding visfatin, mean se-

rum concentrations in breast cancer patients have been reported to be higher at baseline than in control groups [42-44]. In addition, lower systemic visfatin levels have been associated with improved long-term survival and disease remission [42,46]. However, these findings should be interpreted cautiously and should not be considered confirmatory of biomarker utility.

Existing literature indicates that adjuvant therapy is associated with significant alterations in the serum concentrations of the aforementioned adipokines. Trying to interpret our findings, it is essential to consider that these hormones may modulate malignant cellular behavior via specific receptor-mediated pathways. Upon penetrating the basement membrane, breast cancer (BC) cells interact dynamically with adipocytes within the tumor microenvironment (TME) [47]. These specialized cells, termed cancer-associated adipocytes (CAAs), are considered pivotal mediators of disease progression [48]. This bidirectional crosstalk may establish a permissive microenvironment that drives critical oncogenic processes, including cellular proliferation, angiogenesis, invasion, and metastasis [47]. Furthermore, CAAs facilitate systemic communication with both proximal and distal BC cells through the secretion of various bioactive factors, including lipokines [49]. The metabolic interplay between adipocytes and malignant cells appears to be attenuated following the therapeutically induced depletion of the latter. Specifically, the administration of chemotherapeutic agents may disrupt these paracrine and endocrine signaling axes. Such agents exert their effects through diverse mechanisms: fluorouracil impairs DNA synthesis and repair to inhibit proliferation; cyclophosphamide acts as a cytostatic agent during the G2 and S phases; doxorubicin induces direct cytotoxicity; and paclitaxel stabilizes microtubules, thereby arresting the dynamic reorganization essential for interphase and mitotic functions.

Regarding the serum lipid profile—comprising total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-C, and HDL-C—our analysis identified a statistically significant alteration exclusively in triglyceride concentrations when comparing baseline values to post-chemotherapy outcomes [50]. This observation aligns with existing literature [50-51]. Specifically, triglyceride levels exhibited a significant elevation in breast cancer patients following the completion of effective cytotoxic therapy, suggesting a possible association with the systemic effects of adjuvant chemotherapy [51].

This study should be interpreted within an exploratory framework due to the absence of a control group and the relatively small sample size

(n=25), which limit generalizability and do not allow causal conclusions. Potential confounding factors such as BMI variation, menopausal status, dietary variation, systemic inflammation, and chemotherapy-related metabolic effects were not controlled for in the present analysis and should be considered in the context of the study's exploratory design, limited sample size, and absence of a control group. Given the exploratory nature of the study, a simplified statistical approach was applied. Detailed ANOVA outputs, including F-values and degrees of freedom, as well as effect size estimation and confidence intervals, were not reported, and the assumption of sphericity was not formally assessed (e.g., using Mauchly's test) or corrected (e.g., Greenhouse–Geisser or Huynh–Feldt adjustments). Therefore, the findings should be interpreted as exploratory and hypothesis-generating rather than confirmatory.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we observed that the elevated levels of adiponectin following the completion of treatment, together with the reduced concentrations of the other three adipokines identified in our study, are consistent with findings reported in several previous studies. This finding, however, cannot under any circumstances justify the abolition of the widely used indicators in breast cancer (BC). Given that all studies recommend that further research must be conducted prior to their widespread adoption, it is suggested that these adipokines may warrant further investigation as auxiliary parameters in larger controlled studies. Regarding lipids, only triglyceride levels may be considered as an informative parameter for assessing the outcome of chemotherapy.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

ETHICAL STATEMENTS

The study protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the General Anticancer Hospital of Piraeus "METAXA" (reference number 12367/27-01-2021) and the Ethical Committee of the University of West Attica (reference number 11914/17-02-2021). The principles of the Declaration of Helsinki were followed throughout the study involving human subjects. All patients were provided with an informed consent form containing information about the study, and their willingness to participate was confirmed by signature.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) USE

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI. No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

FUNDING

The project is financially supported by ELKE UniWA (Special Account for Research Funds of University of West Attica).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors have contributed equally.

AUTHOR ORCIDs

Nikolaos Dogkas <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7082-4424>

Maria Trapali <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8785-7522>

Christine Fountzoula <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3765-2112>

George Albert Karikas <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8583-5258>

Petros Karkalousos <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1244-8035>

DATA AVAILABILITY

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

REFERENCES

1. Bray F., Ferlay J., Soerjomataram I.: Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 68(6): 394–424 (2018). DOI: [10.3322/caac.21609](https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21609)
2. Siegel R. L., Miller K. D., Fuchs H. E., Jemal A.: Cancer Statistics. *CA Cancer J. Clin.* 72: 7–33 (2022). DOI: [10.3322/caac.21708](https://doi.org/10.3322/caac.21708)
3. Garcia-Estevez L., Moreno-Bueno G.: Updating the role of obesity and cholesterol in breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Res.* 21(1): 35 (2019). DOI: [10.1186/s13058-019-1124-1](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13058-019-1124-1)
4. Vance J. E., Vance D.: Biochemistry of Lipids, Lipoproteins and Membranes. 5th Edition Elsevier. 8-9 (2008).
5. Santos C. R., Schulze A.: Lipid Metabolism in Cancer. *The FEBS Journal.* 279: 2610-2623 (2012). DOI: [10.1111/j.1742-4658.2012.08644](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1742-4658.2012.08644)
6. Hsu P. P., Sabatini D. M.: Cancer Cell Metabolism: Warburg and Beyond. *Cell.* 134: 703-707 (2008). DOI: [10.1016/j.cell.2008.08.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2008.08.021)

7. Hegele R. A.: Plasma Lipoproteins: Genetic Influences and Clinical Implications. *Nature Reviews Genetics*. 10:109-121 (2009).
DOI: [10.1038/nrg2481](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg2481)
8. Rybinska I., Agresti R., Trapani A.: Adipocytes in breast Cancer, the thick and the thin. *Cells*. 9(3): 560 (2020).
DOI: [10.3390/cells9030560](https://doi.org/10.3390/cells9030560)
9. Cha Y. J., Koo J. S.: Adipokines as therapeutic targets in breast cancer treatment. *Expert Opin Ther Targets*. 22(11): 941-53 (2018).
DOI: [10.1080/14728222.2018.1538356](https://doi.org/10.1080/14728222.2018.1538356)
10. Wolin K. Y., Carson K., Colditz G. A.: Obesity and Cancer. *Oncologist*. 15: 556-565 (2012).
DOI: [10.1634/theoncologist.2009-0285](https://doi.org/10.1634/theoncologist.2009-0285)
11. Spyrou N., Avgerinos K. I., Mantzoros C. S., Dalamanga M.: Classic and Novel Adipocytokines at the Intersection of Obesity and Cancer: Diagnostic and Therapeutic Strategies. *Curr Obes Rep*. 7: 260-275 (2018)
DOI: [10.1007/s13679-018-0318-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13679-018-0318-7)
12. Galic S., Oakhill G. S., Steinberg G. R.: Adipose tissue as an endocrine organ. *Mol Cell Endocrinol*. 316: 129-39 (2010).
DOI: [10.1016/j.mce.2009.08.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mce.2009.08.018)
13. Mantzoros C. S., Magkos F., Brinkoetter M., Sienkiewicz E., Dardeno T. A., Kim S-Y.: Leptin in human physiology and pathophysiology. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab*. 301: 567-84 (2011).
DOI: [10.1152/ajpendo.00315.2011](https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpendo.00315.2011)
14. Booth A., Magnuson A., Fouts J., Foster M.: Adipose tissue, obesity and adipokines: role in cancer promotion. *Horm Mol Biol Clin Investig*. 21:57-74 (2015).
DOI: [10.1515/hmbci-2014-0037](https://doi.org/10.1515/hmbci-2014-0037)
15. Lee C. H., Woo Y. C., Wang Y., Yeung C. Y., Xu A., Lam K. S. L.: Obesity, adipokines and cancer: an update. *Clin Endocrinol*. 83:147- 56 (2015).
DOI: [10.1111/cen.12667](https://doi.org/10.1111/cen.12667)
16. Gui Y., Pan Q., Chen X., Xu S., Luo X., Chen L.: The Association between Obesity Related Adipokines and Risk of Breast Cancer: A Meta-Analysis. *Oncotarget*. 8: 75389-75399 (2017).
DOI: [10.18632/oncotarget.17853](https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.17853)
17. Tewari S., Vargas R., Reizes O.: The Impact of Obesity and Adipokines on Breast and Gynecologic Malignancies. *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci*. 1518: 131-150 (2022).
DOI: [10.1111/nyas.14916](https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.14916)
18. Frankenberry K. A., Skinner H., Somasundar P., McFadden D. W., Vona-Davis L. C.: Leptin receptor expression and cell signaling in breast cancer. *Int J Oncol*. 28: 985-93 (2006).
DOI: [10.3892/ijo.28.4.985](https://doi.org/10.3892/ijo.28.4.985)
19. Harris H. R., Tworoger S. S., Hankinson S. E., Rosner B. A., Michels K. B.: Plasma leptin levels and risk of breast cancer in premenopausal women. *Cancer Prev Res*. 4: 1449-56 (2011).
DOI: [10.1158/1940-6207.CAPR-11-0125](https://doi.org/10.1158/1940-6207.CAPR-11-0125)
20. Niu J., Jiang L., Guo W., Shao L., Liu Y., Wang L.: The association between leptin level and breast cancer: a meta-analysis. *PLoS One*. 8: 67349 (2013).
DOI: [10.1371/journal.pone.0067349](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0067349)
21. Nehme R., Diab-Assaf M., Decombat C., Delort L., Caldefie-Chezet F.: Targeting Adiponectin in Breast Cancer. *Biomedicines*. 10: 2958 (2022).
DOI: [10.3390/biomedicines10112958](https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines10112958)
22. Tsankof A., Tziomalos K.: Adiponectin: A Player in the Pathogenesis of Hormone-Dependent Cancers. *Front. Endocrinol*. 13: 2522 (2022).
DOI: [10.3389/fendo.2022.1018515](https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2022.1018515)
23. Simone V., D'Avenia M., Argentiero A. Felici C., Rizzo F.M., De Pergola G., Silvestris F.: Obesity and Breast Cancer: Molecular Interconnections and Potential Clinical Applications. *Oncologist*. 21: 404 (2016).
DOI: [10.1634/theoncologist.2015-0351](https://doi.org/10.1634/theoncologist.2015-0351)
24. Reizes O., Berger N. A.: Adipocytokines, energy balance, and cancer. *Springer International Publishing Switzerland*. 2017.
25. Chen D. C., Chung Y. F., Yeh Y. T., Chaung H. C., Kuo F. C., Fu O. Y.: Serum adiponectin and leptin levels in Taiwanese breast cancer patients. *Cancer Lett*. 237: 109-14 (2006).
DOI: [10.1016/j.canlet.2005.05.047](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.canlet.2005.05.047)
26. Jeong Y. J., Bong J. G., Park S. H., Choi J. H., Oh H. K.: Expression of leptin, leptin receptor, adiponectin, and adiponectin receptor in ductal carcinoma in situ and invasive breast cancer. *J Breast Cancer*. 14: 96-103 (2011).
DOI: [10.4048/jbc.2011.14.2.96](https://doi.org/10.4048/jbc.2011.14.2.96)
27. Papakonstantinou E., Piperigkou Z., Karamanos N. K., Zolota V.: Altered Adipokine Expression in Tumor Microenvironment Promotes Development of Triple Negative Breast Cancer. *Cancers*. 14: 4139 (2022).
DOI: [10.3390/cancers14174139](https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14174139)
28. Wang Y. Y., Hung A. C., Wu Y. C., Lo S., Da Chen H., Chen Y. K., Hsieh Y.C., Hu S. C. S., Hou M.F., Yuan S. S. F.: ADSCs Stimulated by Resistin Promote Breast Cancer Cell Malignancy via CXCL5 in a Breast Cancer Coculture Model. *Sci. Rep*. 12: 15437 (2022).

DOI: [10.1038/541598-022-19290-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/541598-022-19290-6)

29. Georgiou G. P., Provatopoulou X., Kalogera E., Siasos G., Menenakos E., Zografos G. C., Gounaris A.: Serum Resistin Is Inversely Related to Breast Cancer Risk in Premenopausal Women. *Breast*. 29: 163–169 (2016).

DOI: [10.1016/j.breast.2016.07.025](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.breast.2016.07.025)

30. Dalamaga M., Karmaniolas K., Papadavid E., Pelekanos N., Sotiropoulos G., Lekka A.: Elevated Serum Visfatin/Nicotinamide Phosphoribosyl-Transferase Levels Are Associated with Risk of Postmenopausal Breast Cancer Independently from Adiponectin, Leptin, and Anthropometric and Metabolic Parameters. *Menopause*. 18: 1198–1204 (2011).

DOI: [10.1097/gme.0b013e31821e21f5](https://doi.org/10.1097/gme.0b013e31821e21f5)

31. Ghaneialvar H., Shiri S., Kenarkoohi A., Fallah Vastani Z., Ahmadi A., Khorshidi A., Khooz R.: Comparison of Visfatin Levels in Patients with Breast Cancer and Endometrial Cancer with Healthy Individuals: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Health Sci. Rep.* 5: e895 (2022).

DOI: [10.1002/hsr2.895](https://doi.org/10.1002/hsr2.895)

32. Galli M., Van Gool F., Rongvaux A., Andris F., Leo O.: The nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase: a molecular link between metabolism, inflammation, and cancer. *Cancer Res*. 70:8–11 (2010).

DOI: [10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-09-2465](https://doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-09-2465)

33. Park H. J., Kim S. R., Kim S. S., Wee H. J., Bae M. K., Ryu M. H.: Visfatin promotes cell and tumor growth by upregulating Notch1 in breast cancer. *Oncotarget*. 5: 5087–99 (2014).

DOI: [10.18632/oncotarget.2086](https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.2086)

34. Moschen A. R., Kaser A., Enrich B., Mosheimer B., Theurl M., Niederegger H.: Visfatin, an adipocytokine with proinflammatory and immunomodulating properties. *J Immunol*. 178: 1748–58 (2007).

DOI: [10.4049/jimmunol.178.3.1748](https://doi.org/10.4049/jimmunol.178.3.1748)

35. Moschen A. R., Gerner R. R., Tilg H.: Pre-B cell colony enhancing factor/NAMPT/visfatin in inflammation and obesity-related disorders. *Curr Pharm Des*. 16: 1913–20 (2010).

DOI: [10.2174/138161210791208947](https://doi.org/10.2174/138161210791208947)

36. Jardé T., Perrier S., Vasson M. P., Caldefie-Chézet F.: Molecular mechanisms of leptin and adiponectin in breast cancer. *Eur J Cancer*. 47: 33–43 (2011).

DOI: [10.1016/j.ejca.2010.09.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejca.2010.09.005)

37. Kim J. G., Kim E. O., Jeong B. R., Min Y. J., Park J. W., Kim E. S., Namgoong I. S., Kim Y. I., Lee B. J.: Visfatin stimulates proliferation of MCF-7 human breast cancer cells. *Mol Cells*. 30: 341–345 (2010).

DOI: [10.1007/s10059-010-0124-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10059-010-0124-x)

38. Wang Y., Lam J. B., Lam K. S., Liu J., Lam M. C., Hoo R. L., Wu D., Cooper G. J., Xu A.: Adiponectin modulates the glycogen synthase kinase-3beta/beta-catenin signaling pathway and attenuates mammary tumorigenesis of MDA-MB-231 cells in nude mice. *Cancer Res*. 66: 11462–11470 (2006).

DOI: [10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-06-1969](https://doi.org/10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-06-1969)

39. Ahmed S. H., Idrees F., Ahsam M.: Association of serum leptin with serum estradiol in relation to breast carcinogenesis: a comparative case-control study between pre and postmenopausal women. *Turk J Med Sci*. 48(2): 305-10 (2018).

DOI: [10.3906/sag-1704-10](https://doi.org/10.3906/sag-1704-10)

40. Sambiasi D., Summa S., Digennaro M.: Adipokines in hereditary breast cancer patients and healthy relatives. *Oncotarget*. 8(60): 101255-61 (2017).

DOI: [10.18632/oncotarget.21018](https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.21018)

41. Liu J., Lam J. B., Chow K. H.: Adiponectin stimulates Wnt inhibitory factor-1 expression through epigenetic regulations involving the transcription factor specificity protein 1. *Carcinogenesis*. 29(11): 4968 (2008).

DOI: [10.1093/carcin/bgn194](https://doi.org/10.1093/carcin/bgn194)

42. Assiri A. M., Kamel H. F., Hassanien M. F.: Resistin, visfatin, adiponectin, and leptin: risk of breast cancer in pre- and postmenopausal Saudi females and their possible diagnostic and predictive implications as novel biomarkers. *Dis. Markers*. 253519 (2015).

DOI: [10.1155/2015/253519](https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/253519)

43. Assiri A. M., Kamel H. F.: Evaluation of diagnostic and predictive value of serum adipokines: leptin, resistin and visfatin in postmenopausal breast cancer. *Obes. Res. Clin. Pract*. 10: 442–453 (2016).

DOI: [10.1016/j.orcp.2015.08.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orcp.2015.08.017)

44. Kang J. H., Yu B. Y., Youn D. S.: Relationship of serum adiponectin and resistin levels with breast cancer risk. *J. Kor. Med. Sci*. 22: 117–121 (2007).

DOI: [10.3346/jkms.2007.22.1.117](https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2007.22.1.117)

45. Dalamaga M., Karmaniolas K., Papadavid P., Pelekanos N., Sotiropoulos G., Lekka A.: Hyperresistinemia is associated with postmenopausal breast cancer. *Menopause*. 20:845–851 (2013).

DOI: [10.1097/GME.0b013e31827f06dc](https://doi.org/10.1097/GME.0b013e31827f06dc)

46. Li X. Y., Tang S. H., Zhou X. C., Ye Y. H., Xu X. Q., Li R. Z.: Preoperative serum visfatin levels and prognosis of breast cancer among Chinese women. *Peptides*. 51:86–90 (2014).

DOI: [10.1016/j.peptides.2013.11.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peptides.2013.11.010)

47. Pallegar N. K., Christian S. L.: Adipocytes in the Tumor Microenvironment. In: Siemann DW, editor. *Tumor Microenvironment*, 1–13 (2020).
DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-37184-5_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-37184-5_1)
48. Wu Q., Li B., Sun S., Sun S.: Unraveling adipocytes and Cancer links: is there a role for senescence? *Front Cell Dev Biol.* 8 (2020).
DOI: [10.3389/fcell.2020.00282](https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2020.00282)
49. Crake R. L. I., Phillips E., Kleffmann T., Currie M. J.: Co-culture with human breast adipocytes differentially regulates protein abundance in breast Cancer cells. *Cancer Genomics Proteomics.* 16(5):319–332 (2019)
DOI: [10.21873/cgp.20137](https://doi.org/10.21873/cgp.20137)
50. Alexopoulos C. G., Pourmaras S., Vaslamatzis M., Avgerinos A., Raptis S.: Changes in serum lipids and lipoproteins in cancer patients during chemotherapy. *Cancer chemotherapy and pharmacology.* 30(5): 412–6 (1992).
DOI: [10.1007/BF00689971](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00689971)
51. Rzymowska J.: Effect of cytotoxic chemotherapy on serum lipid levels in breast cancer patients. *Pathobiology: journal of immunopathology, molecular and cellular biology.* 67(3): 129–32 (1999).
DOI: [10.1159/000028062](https://doi.org/10.1159/000028062)